



Fig. 1 Appearance of samples produced at initial substrate temperature and tempering temperatures of 80, 180 and 350°C



Fig. 2 Microstructure of H13 steel with preheating and tempering temperature of a) 80 °C, b) 180 °C, c) 350 °C (marker size: 100 µm).



Fig. 3 Microstructure of H13 alloy tempered at 80, 180 and 350°C, magn. 1000x



Fig. 4 Microstructure of H13 alloy tempered at 80, 180 and 350°C, magn. 5000x



Fig. 5 Microstructure of H13 alloy tempered at 80, 180 and 350°C, magn. 10000x



Fig. 6 OIM maps and the corresponding IQ (image quality) maps of the samples tempered at 80, 180 and 350°C



Fig. 7 Average size of martensite plates depending on the substrate and annealing temperatures used



Fig. 8 Fractures of H13 steel annealed at 80, 180 and 350°C observed after impact test



Fig. 9 Tensile curves of Lens produced H13 steel as a function of preheating and annealing/tempering temperature



Fig. 10 Fractures of H13 steel annealed at 80, 180 and 350°C observed after static tensile test



Fig. S1 Surface chemical composition of a sample tempered at 350 °C